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GREEN SYNTHESIS OF ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES FROM *ACTINIDIA DELICIOSA* (KIWI) FRUIT AND EVALUATION OF ITS ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Nanoparticles (NPs) have unique properties compared to their bulk counterparts, and they have potentials for various applications in many fields of life science. Green-synthesized NPs have garnered considerable interest due to their inherent features such as rapidity, eco-friendliness and cost-effectiveness. Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of Saponin, Flavonoids, Steroids, Terpenoids, Triterpenoids. Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) were synthesized using an aqueous extract of *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit samples. The resulting nanoparticles were characterized by using UV-Visible Spectroscopy, Scanning electron microscope (SEM), Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis. The antimicrobial potential of the synthesized ZnO NPs against bacterial and fungal strains was examined by the disk diffusion method, and they showed a promising antibacterial and antifungal potential. The results showed antimicrobial effect of ZnO NPs of *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit samples on the selected Bacterial and Fungal strains.

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INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology deals with the production and usage of material with nanoscale dimension. Nanoscale dimension provides nanoparticles a large surface area to volume ratio and thus very specific properties. Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) had been in recent studies due to its large bandwidth and high exciton binding energy and it has potential applications like antibacterial, antifungal, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, antioxidant and optic properties. Nanotechnology is the production and use of materials at the smallest possible scale [1].

In nanotechnology, a nanoparticle is defined as a small object that behaves as a whole unit in terms of its transport and properties [2]. In the current situation, one of the most promising and therapeutic agents is nanoparticles. Nanoparticles are being viewed as the fundamental building blocks of nanotechnology [3]. In general, metal oxide nanoparticles are inorganic. Various nanoparticles such as Fe, Ni, Co, Mn, and Zn are known as the enormously accepted magnetic materials for a wide range of applications such as various electronic ignition systems, generators, vending machines, medical implants, wrist watches, inductor core, transformer circuits, magnetic sensors and recording equipment, telecommunications, magnetic fluids, and microwave absorbers [4].

Metal-based nanoparticles constitute an effective antimicrobial agent against common pathogenic microorganisms. A multiple of research have established that zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticle has antifungal and antibacterial activity. ZnO is an inorganic compound with the formula ZnO. It usually appears as a white powder, nearly insoluble in water. The powder is widely used as an additive in numerous materials and products including plastics, ceramics, glass, cement, rubber (e.g., car tyres), lubricants, paints, ointments, adhesives, pigments, foods (source of Zn nutrient), batteries, ferrites, and fire retardants. ZnO is present in the earth crust as a mineral zincite; however, most ZnO used commercially is produced synthetically [5].

Green synthesis of nanoparticles has gained significant importance in recent years and has become one of the most preferred methods of the synthesis of nanoparticle. Green synthesis of nanoparticle aims to protect the environment not only by cleaning up but also by inventing new chemical process that does not defile. The uses of plant extracts are far more advantageous than that of other biological methods of synthesis since this process eliminates the tedious task of maintaining microbial medium and cultures [5].

Kiwi fruit is one of the few new fruit crops successfully adopted by international markets in recent years. It has become a high value export crop for a number of countries including New Zealand, Italy, and Chile. It has been reported that folk remedy for adult diseases, such as potent anti-hepatotoxic, anti-pyorrheal and gingival inflammation, was observed in the roots of *Actinidia deliciosa*. The genus *Actinidia* (*Actinidiaceae*) are widely used in Chinese folk medicines to treat such diseases as hepatitis, edema, rheumatoid arthritis, gastric cancer and breast cancer etc. *Actinidia deliciosa* is distributed in west China, and showed to have anti-tumor and protective effects on acute hepatic injury in biological arrays [6].

The extensive use of antibiotics has resulted in emergence of antibiotic resistant organisms. There is need and demand for generating safer and natural therapeutic products for improving health and preventing diseases. Significant work has been done on kiwi leaves and roots but no significant previous study has been reported on whole kiwi fruit [7]. Thus, the aims and objectives of the present study are to green synthesize ZnO nanoparticle using *Actinidia deliciosa* (Kiwi fruit) aqueous extract and to characterize green synthesized ZnO nanoparticle using UV-Visible Spectroscopy, Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis. We also focused on antibacterial activity of green synthesized ZnO nanoparticle using agar well diffusion method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of Kiwi plant material

The fruits of *Actinidia deliciosa* (Fig.1) were purchased in January 2021 from Fruit shop, Thanjavur, Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu, India and authenticated in Botany Department, St. Joseph College, Trichy, Tamilnadu, India.

Fig 1. *Actinidia deliciosa*(Kiwi) fruit during drying and Processing.

SYSTEMATIC SCIENTIFIC CLASSIFICATION:

***Actinidia deliciosa* (Kiwi fruit)**

Kingdom : Plantae
 Division : Magnoliophyta
 Class : Magnoliopsida
 Order : Ericales
 Family : Actinidiaceae
 Genus : *Actinidia*
 Species : *deliciosa*
 Botanical name : *Actinidia deliciosa*

Parts Used : Fruit

Preparation of plant extract:

1 gram of *Actinidia deliciosa* fruits flesh were transferred in to conical flask (250ml). The conical flask containing 50ml of water. The conical flask *Actinidia deliciosa* fruits were shake it well for 30 minutes by free hand. After 24 hrs, the extracts were filtered using whatman filter paper No.1 and filtrate used for further analysis.

Phytochemical Screening:

Chemical tests were carried out on the extract using standard procedures to identify the constituents as described by Sofowara (1993) [8], Trease and Evans (1989) [9].

Quantitative analysis of phytochemicals;

Determination of total phenols by spectrophotometric method, total phenols was estimated as per the method of Edeoga *et al.*, (2005) [10].

Flavonoid and total terpenoids were determined by the method of Bohm and Kocipai-Abyazan (1994) [11].

Synthesis of Zinc oxide nanoparticles:

Preparation of *Actinidia deliciosa* fruits flesh extract

The dried fruits flesh were pulverized well with electric mixer to make a powder. 8 grams of powder sample was mixed in 80 ml of deionized water and the mixture was boiled for 70°C for 20 min. The mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, after cooling the extract was filtered with Whatman No.1 filter paper.

Synthesis of Zinc oxide nanoparticles using fruits flesh extract (Thema *et al.*, 2015) [12]

20 ml of the aqueous extract of *Actinidia deliciosa* fruits flesh was added to 80ml of 0.05 M ZnCl₂. The solution was then transferred to a 200 mL conical flask and boiled at 70°C for 20 min with a magnetic stirrer and a heater until a brown colored precipitate, which marked the completion of the reaction, was observed. The precipitate was collected while the product was dried in the oven at 80 °C for 6 h given a powder.

UV Visible spectroscopic analysis:

The reduction of pure metal ions was examined under UV-Visible analysis. For UV spectrophotometer analysis, the sample is diluted to 1:10 with the deionized water. The reduction of pure metal ions were scanned in the wavelength ranging from 340-800 nm using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer and the characteristic peaks were detected. The peak values of the UV were recorded. Each and every analysis was repeated twice for the spectrum confirmation.

Scanning Electron microscopy (SEM) Analysis:

The particle size and morphology of nanoparticles were analysed by VEGA3- ZEEISS-SEM machine. The dried form of Zinc oxide nanoparticles were sonicated with distilled water, small droplet of Zinc oxide nanoparticles were placed on glass slide and permitted to dry. The ZEEISS-SEM machine was worked at a vacuum of the order of 10⁻⁵ torr. The accelerating voltage is 10 kV.

Determination of antibacterial activity - The antibacterial activity was performed by disc diffusion method [12].

RESULTS

The present study showed the presence of tannin, saponin, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids, triterpenoids, anthraquinone, polyphenol, glycosides and coumarins while absence of alkaloids. (Table 1 and Fig 2). Recently, many studies have proved that the plant extracts act as a potential precursor for the synthesis of nanomaterial in non-hazardous ways. Since the plant extract contains various secondary metabolites, it acts as reducing and stabilizing agents for the bioreduction reaction to synthesized novel metallic nanoparticles.

Table .1. Qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Actinidia deliciosa* extract.

S. No	Phytochemicals	Aqueous extract
1	Tannin	+
2	Saponin	++
3	Flavonoids	++
4	Steroids	++
5	Terpenoids	++
6	Triterpenoids	++
7	Alkaloids	-
8	Anthraquinone	++
9	Polyphenol	+
10	Glycosides	++
11	Coumarins	++

(+) Presence, (++) High concentrations and (-) Absences.

Fig .2: Qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Actinidia deliciosa* extract.

1.Tannin, 2.Saponin, 3.Flavonoids, 4.Steroids, 5.Terpenoids, 6.Triterpenoids, 7.Alkaloids, 8.Anthroquinone, 9.Polyphenol, 10.Glycosides and 11.Coumarins

Quantitative analysis of *Actinidia deliciosa* extract:

In the present study significant amount of phenol, falvonoids and terpenoids were present in *Actinidia deliciosa* and represented in Table 2.

Table.2: Quantitative analysis of phytochemicals in *Actinidia deliciosa*.

Phytochemicals	Result (mg/gm)
Phenol	221.00±15.70
Flavonoids	34.00±2.38
Terpenoid	10.00±0.70

Value were expressed as Mean ± SD for triplicates.

Synthesis of Zinc oxide nanoparticles:

The aqueous metal ion precursors from metal salts are reduced and as a result a colour change occurs in the reaction mixture. This is the first qualitative indication that nanoparticles are being formed. The intensity of color is directly proportional to nanoparticles production. The aqueous Zinc oxide when exposed to *Actinidia deliciosa* extract was reduced in solution, thereby leading to the formation of Zinc oxide hydrosol. During the visual observation, Zinc oxide and *Actinidia deliciosa* extract stirred magnetically showed the yellow mixture after 1hr. The appearance of yellowish-brown (Fig. 3) color is a clear indication for the development of water soluble monodispersed Zinc oxide nanoparticles.

Fig.3: Synthesis of Zinc oxide nanoparticle (ZnONPs) Using *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit extract.

UV Visible spectroscopic analysis of Zinc oxide nanoparticles:

Nanoparticles have optical properties that are sensitive to size, shape, concentration, agglomeration state, and refractive index near the nanoparticle surface, which makes UV/VIS spectroscopy a valuable tool for identifying, characterizing, and studying these materials.

The relative percentage of scatter or absorption from the measured extinction spectrum depends on the size, shape, composition and aggregation state of nanoparticles. Metal nanoparticles may absorb light, scatter light, or both. As a general rule, smaller particles will have a higher percentage of their extinction due to absorption. For example, light scattering by small (2 nm diameter) particles is negligible; the optical spectrum of the nanoparticles, shown below in Fig.4, is almost entirely due to photon absorption by the metal.

Fig. 4: UV Visible spectrum of Zinc oxide nanoparticles using *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit extract.

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) analysis of Zinc oxide nanoparticles:

SEM can produce very high-resolution images of a sample surface, revealing details about less than 1 to 5 nm in size. Due to the very narrow electron beam, SEM micrographs have a large depth of field yielding a characteristic three-dimensional appearance useful for understanding the surface structure of a sample. Under vacuum, electrons generated by a source are accelerated in a field gradient. The beam passes through Electromagnetic Lenses, focusing onto the specimen. As result of this bombardment different types of electrons are emitted from the specimen. Finally the image is displayed on a monitor between 53 to 89nm.(Fig .5).

Figure 5: High resolution scanning electron microscopic (SEM) image of Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnONPs). Spherical shaped ZnONPs size between 53 to 89nm.

Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis of Zinc oxide nanoparticles:

EDX were used to find elemental composition in the reaction mixture. EDS of ZnONPs revealed the presence of pure Zinc (Zn 98.74%) and was the major constituent element compared to oxygen (1.26%) as shown in Table.3 & Fig.6. The EDX reading proved that the required phase of Zinc (Zn) was present in the ZnONPs.

Fig.6: EDX-Spectroscopy view of the synthesis of Zinc oxide using *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit extract.

Table.3: % of elements present in the ZnONPs.

Elements	Atomic number	Series	Weight %	Atomic %
Zn	30	K-series	98.74	93.70
O	8	K-series	1.26	6.30
Total			100	100

Antimicrobial Activity of Zinc oxide nanoparticles:

The antimicrobial effect of Zinc nanoparticles synthesis from *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit extract is presented in Table.4 and Fig.7. The results of the present study showed there is significant antimicrobial effect of this extract against E.Coli and Candida albicans when compared with standard drug. We also observed a significant antimicrobial activity of *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit extract

on all bacterial and fungal strains used in our study.

Table.4: Antimicrobial activity of Zinc oxide nanoparticles *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit extract.

Microbial strains	ZnCl ₂ (30µl)	Plant extract(30µl)	ZnONPs (30µl)	Standard (30µl)
Bacteria				
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (mm)	1.10±0.08	3.80±0.26	8.30±0.58	11.00±0.77
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (mm)	1.00±0.07	3.50±0.24	8.00±0.56	10.80±0.75
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (mm)	0.80±0.05	3.10±0.21	7.60±0.53	10.60±0.74
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i> (mm)	0.70±0.04	2.80±0.19	7.50±0.52	10.10±0.70
Fungal				
<i>Candida albicans</i> (mm)	0.90±0.06	2.90±0.20	6.50±0.45	10.50±0.73
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (mm)	0.60±0.04	2.60±0.18	6.10±0.42	10.20±0.71
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (mm)	0.50±0.03	1.80±0.12	5.80±0.40	9.80±0.68
<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> (mm)	0.30±0.02	0.60±0.04	5.10±0.35	9.60±0.67

Values expressed as Mean ± SD for triplicates.

Bacterial standard: Chloramphenicol

Fungal standard: Fluconazole

Escherichia coli *Staphylococcus aureus*

Bacillus subtilis

Vibrio cholera

Fig.7: Antibacterial Activity of Zinc oxide nanoparticles.

DISCUSSION:

Phytochemical analysis is very helpful in the estimation of some active biological components of medicinal fruit and plants. Present study showed the presence of tannin, saponin, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids, triterpenoids, anthraquinone, polyphenol, glycosides and coumarins while absence of alkaloid in aqueous extract of *Actinidia deliciosa*. The presence of various phytochemicals of this fruit sample is also in agreement with Bushera et.a L, 2009, Ramesh et.al, 2015.[13,14]

The medicinal value of these plants lies in close to chemical substances that create a definite physiological action on the human body. The minor metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, glycosides, and phenols in plant materials, product the medicinal effect when they are utilized in the conventional medical practice. [15].

In recent years ZnO NPs have drawn attention of many researchers for their unique optical and chemical behaviors which can be easily tuned by changing the morphology. Within the large family of metal oxide NPs ZnO NP has been used in various cutting edge applications like electronics, communication, sensor, cosmetics, environmental protection, biology and medicinal industry [16].

Moreover, ZnO NP has a tremendous potential in biological applications like biological sensing, biological labeling, gene delivery, drug delivery and nano-medicine [17] along with its antibacterial, antifungal, acaricidal, pediculocidal, larvicidal and anti-diabetic activities [18].

The time duration of changes in colour varies from chemical to chemical. It is well known that Zinc nanoparticles in aqueous solution due to excitation of surface plasma on vibrations in Zinc nanoparticles [19].

The medicinal value of these plants lies in close to chemical substances that create a definite physiological action on the human body. The minor metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, glycosides, and phenols in plant materials, product the medicinal effect when they are utilized in the conventional medical practice. From these secondary metabolites alkaloids and its derivatives, which played significant role in analgesic, antispasmodic and bactericidal activities. One of the most common biological properties of alkaloids is their toxicity against cells of foreign organisms like bacteria [20].

Flavonoids are free radical scavenger, super antioxidant and strong water soluble, which prevents oxidative cell injury and have strong anticancer activity. Flavonoids apart from their antioxidant protection effects, prevent the initiation, promotion and progression of tumor.[21].

Medicinal plants also are considered an important source because they contain plentiful amounts of antimicrobial agents). Interest has increased in recent years in medicinal plants and herbs to use as a source of bioactive substances in control of human diseases resulted from microorganisms. Many studies have addressed the impact of plant extracts on the growth of microorganisms and thus the possibility of their use in the treatment of some diseases resulting from various microbial infections.[22].

Our results were consistent with previous *in vitro* study which reported the plant antibiotic substances effect appear to be an inhibitor to Gram-positive than Gram-negative bacteria [23].

CONCLUSION

The present study was demonstrated to screen phytochemicals and synthesis of Zinc Oxide nanoparticles from the aqueous extract of *Actinidia deliciosa* (kiwi fruit) samples. Further, we have also assessed the effectiveness of aqueous extracts of *Actinidia deliciosa* against various bacterial and fungal human pathogens. Extracts were effective in inhibiting the growth of both bacterial and fungal strains. Phytochemical analysis ensure that whole fruit of *Actinidia deliciosa* can accumulate many secondary metabolites of medicinal value. Thus, the whole fruit can be exploited as a natural source for harvesting phytochemicals by using advance techniques of extraction, screening, identification. These results explore possibilities of finding out antimicrobial compounds in *Actinidia deliciosa* fruit to prove its clinical potential in treating diseases.

RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Further it is also recommended to isolate the active constituents from *Actinidia deliciosa* (kiwi fruit) and to screen the efficacy of this fruit for the treatment of various diseases by using both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies which might explore the medicinal potential of whole fruit of *Actinidia deliciosa*.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflicts of interest exist for any of the authors of this study.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Nanoparticles	: NPs
Zinc oxide nanoparticles	: ZnO NPs
Zinc Chloride	: ZnCl ₂
Scanning Electron microscopy	: SEM
Zinc Oxide	: ZnO
Energy-dispersive X-ray	: EDX

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